

You've Been Framed - Partial Audio Matching Functionality to Support Framing Analysis

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How can humanities scholars study framing across audiovisual collections? Segments of audiovisual content are being constantly reinterpreted as they are reused and repeated in new contexts. For instance, a clip from a politician's speech from an evening news programme might be repeated in the context of a talk show where it is critiqued by experts; that same segment might be repeated in a radio programme where it serves to support a completely different narrative. When applied across large collections, framing analysis can reveal patterns and biases in the way audiovisual content is reused and topics are represented in media. Some clips are being reused so often that they become canonised in our media memory. Researchers in the field of media studies are particularly interested in studying such phenomena. At the moment this type of research is performed manually by watching and/or listening to large quantities of audiovisual content or by combing through transcripts. In the context of large audiovisual archives, this anecdotal approach is not scalable.

Questions around framing are highly pertinent in the context of research environments, such as the CLARIAH Media Suite - a virtual research space for humanities scholars that enables exploration and analysis of audiovisual collections. Currently, the Media Suite provides tools for exploring data and collections based on existing metadata and automatically generated transcripts. In the context of the European research project AI4Media, the authors of this paper have been exploring how state-of-the-art Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies can further enhance these research possibilities while being aligned with researcher expectations for explainability and transparency when using digital tools.

The focus of this demo paper is on Partial Audio Matching (PAM) functionality developed to support framing analysis in the Media Suite. PAM is a technique that can identify segments in one 'source' audio file that are identical to segments in another 'target' audio file. This matching process is performed on specifically generated audio fingerprint files, which are compact representations of the audio signal. By exporting audio fingerprints for a range of audiovisual items, it becomes possible to trace reuse at archival scale in an automated fashion. The advantage of this technique is that it is not dependent on language - it could be easily applied across multilingual collections since the analysis is based purely on matching audio signals. It works across any audio, whether that is dialogue, music or soundscapes.

The authors have worked on the underlying infrastructure to process both fingerprint extraction and matching at scale, as well as a User Interface that lets Media Suite users select the 'source' and 'target' programmes to perform matching on and get results which link back to the matched segments in the originating audiovisual programmes. This demo is a work-in-progress and we are keen to showcase the potential of this functionality as well as discuss its limitations and open questions that arose during the implementation and user evaluation.

Figure 1: PAM feature interface in the Media Suite showcasing user selection of source content (left side) and target content (right side).

Figure 2: PAM feature interface in the Media Suite showcasing the list of all matched segments.

Figure 3: PAM feature interface in the Media Suite showcasing visualisation of the matched segments within a selected target programme.

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